

OPEN LETTER

Achieving reproducibility in the innovation process

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 1 not approved]

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Abstract

Reproducibility is essential for innovation but is often hard to achieve in practice. One reason for this is a lack of appreciation of what needs to be reproduced and how in each phase of the innovation process. In the discovery phase, conclusions need to be reproduced through orthogonal investigation. In the translation phase, key attributes and outputs of derived products or processes should be reproducible by defining transferable specifications and protocols, whereas in the application phase, the goal is to achieve reproducible performance in real-world environments through appropriate quality assurance systems.

Plain language summary

Reproducibility is essential for innovation but is often hard to achieve in practice. One reason for this is a lack of appreciation of what needs to be reproduced and how, in each phase of the innovation process. In the discovery phase, conclusions need to be reproduced through orthogonal investigation. In the translation phase, key attributes and outputs of derived products or processes should be reproducible by defining transferable specifications and protocols, whereas in the application phase, the goal is to achieve reproducible performance in real-world environments through appropriate quality assurance systems.

Keywords

Innovation, reproducibility, discovery, translation, application

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

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2. **Tim Booth** , DTU, Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

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Introduction

It has been widely reported that there is a reproducibility crisis in science¹⁻⁴ and that the economic and reputational costs of results which cannot be reproduced are likely far higher than the costs of repeating experiments^{5,6}. Others see opportunity in embracing the challenges surrounding reproducibility, for better science teaching⁷ and the creation of reinvigorated innovation ecosystems⁸. There is much advice in the scientific literature about conducting studies that are more likely to be reproducible, most of which is based on three tenets: good study design based on a sound understanding of the underpinning science⁵; robust methodology execution following the study design using appropriately calibrated and maintained equipment operated by trained personnel⁹; and open, transparent reporting of study protocols, measurement procedures, data acquisition and analysis, including algorithms and codes¹⁰. In addition to this however, as illustrated in Figure 1, we propose that the three major phases of the innovation process, namely discovery, translation and application, represent different contexts in which to consider reproducibility and thus a different approach is required for each.

The discovery phase typically involves demonstration of basic principles to proof-of-concept, representing a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) from 1–3¹¹. In this initial phase, it is the reproducibility of the original conclusion that is paramount, which needs to be more than producing the same result in the same way. To provide sufficient confidence in a discovery for the innovation process to progress, it is necessary to arrive at the same conclusion via multiple orthogonal routes, i.e., independent demonstrations of the same conclusion. In other words, epistemic parity needs to be achieved by establishing that the same conclusion can be reached using a range of methodologies that generate their own appropriate data. Hence, it is important that new knowledge arising from the discovery is described in a manner that facilitates the design of appropriate orthogonal confirmatory routes.

The translation phase of the innovation process is from laboratory demonstration of a prototype (TRL 4) to full-scale demonstration in an environment representing the real world (TRL 6). In this phase, the prototype product or process must be reproducible in terms of predefined attributes and outputs associated with fulfilling its purpose. For this, it is essential to have transferable specifications and protocols that allow prototype products and processes to be deployed in different representative environments by different users while achieving parity of operation and output. When describing an element of a specification or a step in a protocol therefore, the appropriate level of detail is needed, neither too little nor too much, together with the rationale for including particular elements or steps.

The final phase covers demonstration in the operational environment (TRL 7) of an operational product or process (TRL 9), termed the application phase. Here the aim is to achieve parity in overall performance. Customers expect reliability in products and processes, i.e., that they will perform in a consistent manner over time. This requires both robustness in the design of the final product or process and the implementation of appropriate quality assurance procedures so that the expected success rate is achieved across both production items and their lifecycle. Delivery of a consistent success rate is the form of reproducibility expected in the application phase of the innovation process. If an organisation fails to deliver this form of reproducibility, then it is unlikely to be commercially successful or viable.

It is usual for each of the three phases of the innovation process to be undertaken by separate groups of people, often in different organisations with differing motivations and incentives. Discovery generally occurs in research laboratories in universities or specialist research institutes where the drivers are advancing science, publishing scientific papers and attracting funding. Translation is often performed in applied research

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the three phases of the innovation process and how to approach reproducibility in each.

organisations that have a specific mission and setup to bridge the gap between discovery and application. The application phase is predominantly undertaken by commercial organisations when they see the potential of a new product or process to generate revenue and capture market share. In some scenarios these distinctions are blurred, for example when a university spinout company attempts to pursue the entire innovation process. While this blurring can avoid the creation of silos that can stall innovation, it also has the potential to cause a failure to recognise the different contexts of reproducibility in the phases of the innovation process.

In conclusion, successful innovation requires a better understanding and appreciation of the philosophical, contextual and practical differences in establishing reproducibility within the discovery, translation and application phases of the

innovation process. This will improve the design, conduct and outcomes of reproducibility studies and facilitate more fruitful discussion and cooperation between key actors.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are those of the authors. Publication in Open Research Europe does not imply endorsement by the European Commission.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

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Open Peer Review

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Tim Booth

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The authors argue that reproducibility, a cornerstone of scientific and technological credibility, must be understood in relation to three distinct phases of the innovation process: i) Discovery, ii) Translation, and iii) Application. Each phase is associated with different reproducibility criteria: epistemic confirmation for discovery, specification transferability for translation, and performance consistency for application. These phases are mapped to Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), offering a structured lens to evaluate reproducibility across the innovation lifecycle.

The conceptual framing of reproducibility in innovation in terms of these three phases is a thoughtful attempt to bridge epistemological concerns from academia with operational needs in industry. This appears to be a novel and potentially impactful contribution, particularly for research managers and policymakers. However, the letter does not sufficiently distinguish itself from prior work on the reproducibility crisis in academic contexts, nor does it fully resolve tensions between academic and industrial interpretations of reproducibility.

Data and methodology

This is a conceptual piece without original data, but the reasoning is generally coherent. However, the proposal would strongly benefit from concrete examples or case studies illustrating how reproducibility efforts differ (or should differ) across TRLs.

Terminology: The authors' use of "reproducibility" to cover what is elsewhere called "replicability" or "repeatability" may confuse readers, especially in computational and biomedical domains where these terms have distinct meanings. While some justification is provided through epistemological framing, a clearer acknowledgment of prior work that sharpens the definition of competing terminologies (e.g. refer 1, refer 2) would improve clarity and credibility. Readers may disagree that confirmation of conclusions through orthogonal experimental routes qualifies as reproducibility. Conversely, if one cannot independently verify a conclusion using different methods, samples, and data, it might be difficult to argue that the original conclusion is not reproducible in a precise sense, rather than irreplaceable in the current investigation. The paper

would benefit from a more explicit justification of the terminology used, particularly the umbrella use of "reproducibility" in light of current consensus in relevant fields such as computational science, engineering, and biology.

Further, if the aim is to influence innovation practice, the authors should enrich the article by proposing concrete tools or mechanisms (for example, protocol repositories, QA systems, or documentation practices) that could enhance reproducibility at each phase. This would allow stakeholders to more easily action the authors' recommendations.

Many references are drawn from biomedical sciences. Inclusion of examples from materials science, computer science, or engineering would help the piece resonate across more disciplines. While biomedical sciences have naturally dominated the literature on reproducibility due to high stakes, system complexity, and challenges in methodological transparency, there is a wide acknowledgement of the problem across fields.

In their effort to encompass and speak to as many stakeholders as possible, the authors risk conflating issues in reproducibility of knowledge generation (academic) with those of production and deployment (industrial). The three-phase breakdown used by the authors is a positive step, though arguably, it is the challenges in the Discovery phase that lie at the heart of most reproducibility concerns. The Translation and Application steps, for example, rarely require communication of protocols to other stakeholders for reasons of industrial competition and secrecy. It is difficult to imagine start-ups spending much time assisting other start-ups in reproducing their competitive advantage, or incumbent industry leaders helping competitors achieve parity. The authors might assist readers by clarifying the specific issues in phases ii) and iii).

Several minor language issues (such as missing commas or slightly awkward constructions) could be addressed with a careful copy-edit.

Conclusions

The article makes a worthwhile conceptual contribution by linking reproducibility concerns to the innovation pipeline and suggesting that different forms of reproducibility are relevant at different stages. However, in its current form, the piece straddles the boundary between commentary and actionable guidance without fully satisfying either mode. With the addition of clearer definitions, concrete examples, and interdisciplinary breadth, the article could be a useful resource for those involved in translational research, policy, and innovation governance.

Recommendation

Major revision. The core idea is solid but requires clarification, expansion, and sharper framing to fully realize its potential contribution.

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Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is

explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: 2D Materials, Innovation

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 19 February 2025

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Antunes Benjamin

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This open letter discusses reproducibility in science. The paper proposes that the innovation process is divided into three categories: discovery, translation, and application. It states that reproducibility concerns vary across these categories.

For the first category, the focus is on the reproducibility of scientific conclusions. For the second, it concerns the reproducibility of the protocols and processes used to develop the product. For the third, it addresses the reproducibility of the final quality of the product, which is essential for

commercial success.

For all these stages, they use the “Technology Readiness Level” (TRL) scale, that is a “tool for assessing the maturity of technologies during complex system development” to measure the maturity of the project.

My comments:

The introduction of this paper begins by presenting the challenges we face regarding the reproducibility of published research papers. In my opinion, the references cited [1-10] primarily address academic research, particularly the lack of reproducibility in published studies (due to multiple reasons, such as not sharing the data, the code, bad statistics, ...). The paper also provides some clarification on three key tenets they consider essential for reproducibility: good study design, robust methodological execution, and open science, which includes sharing code, data, etc.

However, it seems that the authors then shift their focus to industrial processes rather than academic research. In my view, concerns about reproducibility in industry differ from those in academic research. In science (academia), our objective is to build knowledge upon the existing knowledge of others. The reproducibility crisis mentioned in the introduction refers to this issue: if research papers cannot be reproduced, it raises concerns about the reliability of published results and our ability to build upon previous research.

In an industrial context, however, a probable goal of the company is growth and profitability. Of course, standardizing the products they sell is essential (as discussed in the "application" category), but can we truly talk about reproducibility in this context? A company may aim for internal reproducibility, but its objective might not be to make its protocols and processes (category “translation”) or its final quality assurance (category “application”) easily reproducible by others.

Therefore, in my opinion, this paper might be mixing these two distinct concepts: the reproducibility crisis in academic research (which pertains to scientific publications) and the industrial processes a company establishes to produce and sell standardized products. I fail to see the relevance of considering the latter in this discussion in the context of reproducibility.

A scientific publication is an innovation in itself; it does not necessarily have to lead to the commercialization of a new product. In practice, only a very small percentage of scientific publications result in the production and commercialization of new products.

More focused comments:

The paper uses the TRL scale to describe the maturity of a project. While this may be well-suited for industrial projects, I am unsure whether it effectively applies to scientific publications. The discovery phase corresponds to TRL levels 1 to 3, which include: *Basic principles observed and reported, Technology concept and/or application formulated and Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept.*

The paper states *“In this initial phase, it is the reproducibility of the original conclusion that is paramount, which needs to be more than producing the same result in the same way”.*

First, in my opinion, a published paper is a complete entity in itself. The process of reaching a conclusion is not limited to TRL levels 1 to 3. The tools and methods used—such as code, data, and

other resources—significantly influence the final result and, consequently, the conclusion. I believe that a scientific publication is a project/innovation on its own, and this is where the reproducibility crisis lies, as well as the reproducibility issues highlighted in the references cited by the authors.

Secondly, in the context of scientific research, the current consensus is not to use the term “reproducibility” when referring to obtaining the same scientific conclusion using a different method. In this context, the appropriate term is “replicability.” However, I acknowledge that in epistemology, “reproducibility” remains the broader term. Here are some references:

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<https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

“As a result of discussions with the National Information Standards Organization (NISO), it was recommended that ACM harmonize its terminology and definitions with those used in the broader scientific research community, and ACM agreed with NISO’s recommendation to swap the terms “reproducibility” and “replication” with the existing definitions used by ACM as part of its artifact review and badging initiative. ACM took action to update all prior badging to ensure consistency”

Conclusion:

Overall, in conclusion, I feel that I did not fully grasp the purpose of the article. Perhaps the issue is on my side. I believe that both the references cited and my own perspective focus more on the reproducibility of scientific research papers—whether academic or industry-based—, due to lack of data, code, and so on, while this article seems to address the reproducibility of industrial processes for producing a final commercial product.

However, in this context, no specific tools are proposed. I am not an expert of industry, but considering the concept of reproducibility (if the entity producing and selling the final product wants everyone to be able to reproduce it), the authors could have suggested tools for different phases. For the discovery phase, they could have introduced tools for sharing code, data, or documentation methods. For the translation phase, maybe some workflow tools that facilitate process replication could have been discussed. For the application phase, maybe standardized quality assurance methods might have been relevant.

Additionally, for a general-purpose paper on reproducibility, the references seem overly concentrated on biology (or related fields).

Maybe I didn't grasp the interest of this publication. I am open for discussion.

Some typos:

Abstract:

Missing comma between “how” and “in”: One reason for this is a lack of appreciation of what needs to be reproduced and how in each phase of the innovation process.

Introduction:

Miss comma between “this” and “however”: In addition to this however, as illustrated

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Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Not applicable

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Reproducibility in computer science

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.
